

An exploration into the illusive world of cyberspace and
the anomic trickster like discourse it facilitates.

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Abstract:

Research question(s): (1) social media allows for the idealised presentation of self even if it is inaccurate in its depiction, does the ability to present a falsified self, increase the propensity in the adoption of trickster discourse in reason?

(2) “How, in conditions of anomie can cyber-ecosystems, spring up and re-constitute themselves into new microcosms?”

Cyberspace has permeated all aspects of contemporary life and can prove challenging for researchers to determine its illusive nature; the purpose of this research is to show that the perspectives provided by anthropology can prove invaluable when conducting research online. What is to follow is an auto-netnographic account, with the application of originally formulated theoretical framework of anomie and trickster to interpret field experience. The theoretical foundations of this study are drawn from the three disciplines of criminology and sociology with a strong orientation toward anthropology in order to provide a holistic, blended approach to the study. The following is not by any means a superimposition of theories which are seen fit to interpret specific cyber-anomic phenomenon, but what is on offer is a rather new and insightful way to derive greater understanding about this neglected area of study. To date, Anthropology and its associated disciplines have offered little contribution to the understanding of reproduction and variation in cyber- anomic structure and one of the main objectives is to open-up academic conversation surrounding the relationship between humans and cyber space. What is offered by this study is an in-depth exploration into the systemic deception which persists in cyber space, a far stretch from the indigenous of Papua New Guinea, the Adivasi of India and the many more fascinating people(s) and cultures most often described in anthropological literature. Ultimately humans are behind their online personas and behind every S.M.S message claiming to be a Nigerian prince promising a huge dowry, to a fraudulent message from a random stranger on Facebook claiming ‘YOU’VE WON A PRIZE, please enter in your online banking details!’, It is important not to forget that they are autonomous individuals with personal agendas. The implication of this research has shown that a cynical approach should be upheld when conducting research online as deception has a deep embeddedness within this environment which we share a symbiotic relationship with.

Keywords: Anomie, trickster, Cyberspace, Reciprocity, Anthropology

Introduction

This section will provide brief introduction, fist by discussing the academic context, followed by the research problem, the research aims, objectives, opinions and lastly a discussion in the significance of this work within academia. The study of cyberspace forces one to consider the relationship between humans and emerging social playing fields facilitated by such technology. It is necessary to continually revise and re-adapt methods of research to fill in a gap which has a tendency to widen at a rapid rate which poses

challenges to researchers who struggle to keep-up. This very premise is characterised by Robert Kozinets in his, 'netnography', 'this is a world within a world deeply affecting the world. Fast current, zooming by, expanding, connecting everything to everything'. (Kozinets Robert, 2020,p.4)

The specific issue within this field is the fact that it is still very new in academic spheres and there is no agreed about, equivocal way to approach the study of cyberspace within anthropology and related disciplines. There is evident lack of research in the world of academia between the mediation of what is determined appropriate and inappropriate social media usage, governed by the normative values attached to its use. In short, there exists a gap within the literature which fails at examining the interplay between cyberspace and the establishment of inter-personal relationships through this medium. Given the lack of research in this area and the issues posed by no agreed about way to conduct research online, this is the niche the study aims at filling. The research sought to address the aforementioned factors with application of specific research objectives and methodological practices. This research aims at exploring how cyberspace creates an environment of systemic deception, one which experiences rapid rates of flux and change. The significance this research poses is a new way to conduct research online offering unique perspective and methods of interpretive analysis which show universal variables in the deceptive use of cyber space. What this research will demonstrate is that the majority of the time anything presented through cyberspace is either falsified or an incorrect overly exaggerated narrative for the optimised presentation of self. The intended trajectory of this study is to demonstrate, how there remains a single, stable variable and that is, cyber ecosystems reproduce by effectively breaking down and reconstituting themselves with the development of specific SOP'S, which serve to function in the establishment of trust and therefore ultimately aid in the establishment of human relationships through cyberspace.

Theory

What is to follow is a brief overview of the main theoretical frameworks underpinning this study and my rationale in their selection. The main theory I will be applying to my autoethnographic report(s) is the theory of Anomie because in my view it best helps interpret the deceptive and fraudulent phenomenon I witnessed whilst in the field, and it is also one of the more dominant criminological paradigms which persist to date since its original formulation by Durkheim in 1893. The first mention of Anomie was in Durkheim's work, 'The division of labour in society', in which he refers to dominant cultural ideals and people's gravitation toward them. Durkheim's successor, Merton builds upon the initial criminogenic theory, with more emphasis on the means to achieve culturally defined goals. Considering the perspectives of both academics this provides a well-rounded view of anomie and in this regard, anomie may be seen as, culturally defined goals with the lack of institutional means to achieve such goals thus

resulting in the transgression of both morality and law with the use of illegitimate means to achieve such culturally defined goals. What is highly illuminating is that some socio-cultural environments are either more or less anomic than another with variation depending on the geographical distribution of offenders, anomie is therefore orchestrated by its conditionality, and the conditions of cyber space are more than optimal for this to occur.

In the traditional sense Anomie, its application and inherent effects have been studied in relation to the conditions of a specific region. This in part is highly relevant in the theory's scope, however with cyber space there is no such borders, regions or external factors such as economics to make sweeping generalisations in helping explain why the environment is more anomic than others, so therefore my own application of Anomie has been tweaked to a micro- level approach because I found it was much more appropriate to examine different instances of deviant behaviour on a case-by-case basis. I theorised that because cyber space is difficult to police and in terms of risk assessment there is less likelihood in being held accountable for one's misdeeds cyber-space may therefore be classified as an anomic environment. In the Durkheimian sense cyberspace does not create an environment of normlessness but rather a momentary state of what is referred to as *Déréglement* which provokes individual response. This furthers my argument about the relevance of anomie and shows how well fitted the theory is when tweaked to explore the micro rather than macro in the analysis and interpretation of criminogenic and fraudulent phenomenon conducted via cyber-space.

The second most important theoretical framework I applied in the study is that of the Trickster, and I am going to begin with introducing this idea through the contribution of C. J. Jung and the work of both Agnes Horvath and Arpad Szakolczai in their book 'The political sociology and Anthropology of evil: Tricksterology'. The figure of the trickster is endemic to the human psyche and serves as a metaphor which has been repeated time and time again throughout human histories in a multitude of different forms. The trickster is representative of man's under-developed state of human consciousness and myths of the trickster exist for us to consider and be reminded of the origin in humanities conscious mind. 'The so-called civilised man has forgotten the trickster. He remembers him by only figuratively and metaphorically, when irritated by his own ineptitude, he speaks of fate playing tricks on him or of things being bewitched' (Radin Paul, Kerényi Karl, C.J Jung, 1957 pp269). Arpad shares some of these same views stating that metaphors of the trickster are, 'seemingly universal and timeless, capturing allegedly some inevitable and dark features of human nature'. (Horvath Agnes, Szakolczai Arpad,2020, pp.25) This would suggest that the trickster can manifest in our very own human nature, thus implicating anyone may embody trickster logic.

The basic principle of this theory is that humans, whilst having positive attributes also have a sinister side with connection to the origin of humanities conscious mind, one that makes us act in our own self-interest and doing so by any means necessary and in a certain manner which allows for the transgression of morality without any assumption of responsibility for one's misdeeds. 'The trickster teaching ducks to sing with closed eyes so that he could wring their necks one by one', (Horvath Agnes, Szakolczai Arpad,2020, pp.31) this metaphor indicates that people are misled using trickster logic to such a great degree that they are desensitised to what is happening in their immediate environment. Introducing the concept of the trickster is difficult because it is hard to imagine what one would look like due to its ability to change into a multiplicity of different forms. The classical embodiment of the trickster archetype in my view, originates from classical literature, more specifically a court jester by the name of Feste in Shakespeare's play 'the twelfth night'. The majority if not all of Feste's monologue is nonsensical, yet Feste has a great deal of wisdom and one of his most famous phrases is, "better a Whitty fool, than a foolish wit"(Shakespeare William, 1602, act-1, scene-5). This is where I begin to introduce the trickster in my studied environment, the trickster makes one believe that they are lacking knowledge whilst this certainly is not the case, and this is where the danger lies with the trickster, resulting in total disillusionment. This historical archetype is outdated in the sense that the horizon has shifted, and it is also indicative of the type

of fluidity of the trickster in the assumption of different forms. I feel as though in contemporary society ‘the catfish’ has become the modern embodiment of trickster logic and this is what I will explore in the following autoethnographic account.

Paradoxically we create trickster archetypes to fear whilst also at times embodying its logic, throughout history the trickster has been depicted in innumerable forms, however there is a stable variable and that is, the trickster has always been depicted with some human characteristics but at the same time it is never quite human. A key example of this is the archetypal representation of the trickster in modernity as the clown. A recent body of study has aimed to explain why many people are afraid of clowns and the data has shown that there is a far deeper, more instinctual fear and repulsion which stems from the idea of contagion and deformity, which is termed ‘the uncanny valley phenomenon’. The study did not fail to mention that indeed there are external influences which may exacerbate the fear of clowns in modernity, However it does beg the question, just as human biology has evolved to steer clear of deformity and disease, alternatively ‘the not quite human’ has the development of human consciousness followed a similar route of development? and have the stories of the trickster always permeated societies of both past and present to show the imminent danger of the trickster and the subsequent consequences of this social pathology? It is quite evident that in modernity there are more tricksters than ever before, and the story of the trickster is the embodiment of the fear in human regression to our past, underdeveloped state of consciousness and the stories act to dissuade us from using its logic.

The theory of Anomie and the Trickster are rather complimentary in the sense that Anomie sets out to explain how the institution can increase the use of illegitimate means to achieve culturally defined goals and the theory of the trickster entails that the illegitimate means and transgression of boundaries is a key component to human nature. The trickster ties in well to the theory of anomie and works in conjunction with the dualism between the contribution of both Durkheim and Merton in the sense that Durkheim placed more emphasis on the gravitation toward culturally defined goals and the trickster logic entails that ‘there is nothing original about the trickster, because its entire purpose is to imitate. The trickster can only ever imitate things, never doing anything with full participation and inner conviction.’ (Horvath Agnes, Arpad Szakolczai,2020 pp.25). Thus, implicating that humans are ultimately driven by the mimetic desire to have or achieve like the other and as Durkheim emphasised this relates to strong feelings of gravitation toward culturally defined goals. While on the other hand Merton’s contribution to this theory with the addition of lack of institutional means to achieve goals, this also functions extremely well with the theory of the trickster as ‘The Trickster fails to respect all limits and keep order, this situation is rather perplexing, as the trickster essentially belongs to the limit being nothing more but a figure of the threshold, a boundary marker even a mediator.’ (Horvath Agnes, Arpad Szakolczai,2020, pp.108).

Review of literature

The purpose of the literature review to follow is to provide a fully comprehensive overview of the major academic works cited throughout the course of this study, and to synthesise literature in relation to the research aims and objectives. The following research question(s) are. **(1)** Social media allows for the idealised presentation of self even if it is inaccurate in its depiction, does the ability to present a falsified self, increase the propensity in the adaptation of trickster discourse in reason? And **(2)** How, in conditions of anomie can cyber-ecosystems, spring up and re-constitute themselves into new microcosms? The main research objective is to demonstrate how deception is deeply rooted in the human experience of cyber space and how this serves to function. The scope of the literature has seen continued revisions throughout the course of this study to fit within the research aims. At times the scope of literature was proving far too wide, however the type insights provided from such a large scope hold relevance in shaping the trajectory of the work and decision was made to include such contributions here. The prospective structure of the literature review will be organised with topics into their relevant themes and sub-headings and will aim to show the progression in thought process throughout the study and display how the chosen academic literature has acted as the catalyst which continually shifted the conceptual awareness.

Anomie and Trickster:

The theory of anomie is applied to derive understanding in the transgression of norms within society. Anomie was explored, first through the original theorists, Émile Durkheim in 'The division of labour in society'(1893), and Robert K. Merton's, 'Social structure and Anomie'(1938), both works would prove insightful in shaping the theoretical framework which was originally focused on environmental conditions creating systems of anomie. Exploring the topic of anomic systems, the original scope of literature was far reaching and the main objective was to explore the variation of geo-graphical conditions which produced either more or less anomic inducing effects, however this was not explored much further due to the particular time horizon of the study, but hold relevance in shaping the structure of the study. The academic texts which explored this issue were, Jonathan Lusthaus 'Industry of Anonymity'(2018) and 'A culture of corruption: everyday deception and popular discontent in Nigeria' by Daniel Jordan Smith. Both original thinkers Emile Durkheim and Robert K. Merton had varying stance, however Durkheim's characterisation of anomie resonated more closely with the research objectives and the course of direction in study was changed accordingly. Drawing from Durkheim's stance Stejepan G. Mestrovic and Ronald Lorenzo in their work, 'Durkheim's concept of Anomie and the abuse at Abu Ghraib'(2008), explore the concept of Anomie through Déréglement which differs from the functionalist perspective of normlessness, in this view norms exist but a lack of co-ordination implicates induced, momentary states of normlessness, this very premise influenced the research design with emphasis on either more or less anomic inducing effects.

The trickster concept was explored through Paul Radin's, 'The trickster: A study in American Indian mythology' (1987) and Arpad Szakolczai and Agnes Horvath, 'the political sociology and anthropology of evil: tricksterology' (2019). Both accounts of trickster were invaluable in the formulation of such abstract topic and made the concept more digestible. Paul Radin's trickster and C.J Jung's commentary in the work heavily influenced the type of stance taken within the study. Blended perspective was employed with incorporation of other academics which suggest that the trickster discourse is embedded in the human psyche, similar papers have suggested this also, most notably in Metman Philip's 'The trickster figure in schizophrenia'(1958) and John Layard's, 'note on the autonomous psyche and the ambivalence of the trickster concept'(1958). Both theories are not original to the research however, the application of both in interpretive analysis is original in its design.

The Catfish:

Existing literature on catfishing has established that there is very clear distinction between appropriate and inappropriate social media usage, this is most evidently seen in Michael Lovelock's (2017) 'Catching a catfish: constructing the "good" social media user in reality television. What this academic work has highlighted is that popular culture perpetuates the idealised presentation of self through the internet, and places a premium on authenticity, this would implicate that there exists shared values and attitudes with the authentic presentation of self through the internet. However there exists a great deal of moral ambiguity surrounding internet usage which simultaneously allows for a filtered self, yet solicits disapproval by this very premise, 'adult attachment and online dating deception: a theory modernised'(2020) and similarly, 'What lies behind the filter?' uncovering the motivations for using augmented reality (AR) face filters on social media and their effect on wellbeing'(2022). Both academic works examine deception in online dating and the presentation of self, with focus on the individual providing logical reasoning as to why someone would engage in active deceit when dating online. What has already been established within contemporary literature is that there is certain norms, values and attitudes which govern the use of the internet, and certain individuals transgress these norms by depictive inaccuracy. A recurring aspect in the contemporary literature places heavy emphasis on the 'individual', and to date has not been explored through a wider theoretical frame of analysis, this is where contemporary literature stops and where this study gains momentum filling the gap in providing

reasoning as to how certain strain(s) result in transgression of the already distinguished values and attitudes. How contemporary literature connects with my own is that it deals with some of the main issues, such as working to understand the effects of such a highly filtered social environment on individuals and the type of problems which may arise as direct result of this, however what is lacking in contemporary literature and the 'gap' which this study hopes to address is appropriate theoretical engagement in the interpretation of such phenomenon. The catfish is thus explored as the new archetype of trickster discourse in modernity, and using a combination of both Durkheim's concept of anomie and blended view of trickster discourse the following study aims at interpretive analysis of the catfish within modernity to explore deliberate forms of deception conducted through cyberspace.

Methodology

The main objective of this study was to explore the proliferation of deception in cyber space, with intentional and targeted forms of deceit, explored through 'the trickster as catfish'. When required to become enmeshed in participatory observation and analysis of target demographics and individuals I strongly believe the type of research strategy should be adapted accordingly, there is no such thing as objectivity as we are all our own subjective selves. Due to the particular research philosophy as outlined prior, subjectivity has naturally taken precedence and has informed the choice in adoption of interpretive analysis. The main benefit which may be reaped from the strategic application in its approach is the increased understanding in the other(s) point of view with more fair, balanced and accurate representation. In the onset of the study and throughout, the appropriate measure in reasoning was inductive with a bottom up style of approach as the data was both simultaneously gathered and experienced which needed continual reconfiguration to fit the trajectory of this study as a confirmatory approach was applied. The type of study carried out was qualitative and places emphasis on the general rather than the particular, the gathered data and recount of field experiences needed appropriate theoretical engagement which at times also needed slight re-configuration, the theoretical framework of Anomie and Trickster is original in its amalgamation and was most appropriate to fit within the research design. The research strategy implemented was auto-netnography to explore the trickster as catfish and the time horizon was cross sectional to fit within the constraints of research and took place over a six month period. The sampling strategy used was non-probability convenient sampling, the choice of which was dictated by the application of inductive reasoning with the ease in access to demographics.

The mode of data collection for the study entailed keeping a detailed and compiled account of personal interactions and experiences, the use of a field journal was particularly useful to document any thoughts, insights, ideas and opinions in a structured and coherent fashion. The auto-netnographic account was conducted via reddit and entailed reading shared accounts of catfishing encounters posted by users and the examination of the reactions such stories solicited. The second mode of data collection was a reviewal of existing literature on the topic in order to be equipped with the knowledge to comprehend the types of academic conversation taking place and to aid in the formulation of a well-rounded view and to find a gap within the literature. The method of data analysis employed within the study was thematic in nature, with the collection of data through participant observation and the compilation of data into particular groups and recurrent themes, the justification for thematic analysis were the research aims and objectives the study wished to achieve. After the data was compiled and arranged in an orderly manner into distinguished categories the data was analysed through the originally formulated theoretical model of the trickster and anomie. The trickster and anomie are not originally formulated ideas, however what is original in its design

is the amalgamation of both theories in interpretive analysis of social phenomenon. I argue that whilst studying a highly filtered social environment there is need for a tailored theoretical model to aid in effective engagement, and in this regard the combination of both theories, trickster and anomie work well together in the formulation of interpretive analysis of such phenomenon.

The following is a consideration of ethics. All research design choices were implemented in liaison with ethical viability in mind, this was characterised by the change in course of direction with the study as it was difficult to obtain consent from participants dealing with an online environment. Due to the ethical responsibility one has as a researcher it was not appropriate to continue in this fashion, so therefore an auto-netnographic style in approach was used. The procedure of data collection followed strict ethical conduct, participant observation entailed entering into more open forums of discussion shared throughout reddit, and didn't require joining a group, thus the choice of sampling method was non-probability convenient sampling and was chosen with careful consideration of ethics, participant observation followed similar route with strict ethical procedure, this entailed entering into reddit forums and establishing my presence as a researcher which allowed for transparency between researcher and participant. Robert Kozinets book, 'netnography' sets a standard in ethically viable practices and sets strict ethical guidelines when conducting research online. The book proved useful throughout the course of my research and was a credible and ethically viable source to draw from and adhere to. To avoid breach of ethics I have taken a highly generalised approach drawing from the particular to create the general. Data was collected upon entering the reddit scene and establishing my presence as a researcher, this was met with a great deal of unease and apprehension, and due to this I made the decision for auto-netnography taking into consideration the welfare of participants. The change in direction of study and research design were both ethically informed decisions to protect both the welfare of participants and to be able to still continue with my research.

A large part about conducting research is the acceptance of certain limitations, one of the major limitations experienced whilst conducting the study was siphoning out actors true motives and intentions which has proven challenging at times as every interaction had to be taken at face value, there are also the increased propensity and risk associated with being submerged in a social playing field with increased trickster discourse of reason. Identifying the true motives and intentions of actors has always been an area of concern for anthropologists even in traditional ethnography as there is never clear certainty that your participants are being truthful. The issue of truthfulness and conveying the correct narrative is exacerbated when subjects are not within your immediate environment as there is no possible way to pick up on social cues. There is always opportunity for satire and comedy to be misconstrued as truth. There were efforts made to combat the aforementioned limitations and this was through trial and error. Throughout the course of research, an important stance to take was a critical awareness about the opportunity to be deceived and finding credible pools of information with genuine accounts of experience. There is also opportunity for error as the human memory is not all that reliable at times and there is opportunity for misinterpretation. The benefits of this study far outweigh the shortcomings and provide holistic and accurate depiction of field experience with new and insightful methods of theoretical perception and analysis, there is an acceptance that more research is needed to explore the catfish and hopes that the value of this work is at the very least a ripple in the academic conversation to date.

The Trickster as Catfish

Catfishing is a term used to describe the false assumption of an identity on the internet in pursuance of monetary gain or to derive gratification from the active deception of others. 'The Catfish' exploits the human primordial need for companionship and subsists in the online dating sphere in contemporary social life. According to recent studies approximately 19% of internet users in the United States alone are active users on at least one dating platform. (Andrej Hadji-Vasilev, 25th June 2022). This is a highly substantial percentage and puts into context the increased use of dating sites in the procuring of a mate in contemporaneity. This increased use and reliance of online dating platforms doesn't come without its associated risks with some actors utilising dating platforms to create false representations of oneself, or worse yet the creation of an entirely new persona. Academia to date has offered little contribution as so far to explain the phenomenon of catfishing, with psychological studies providing some of the best insights. Online dating deception is used to "increase their mate potential and foster a relationship they would not otherwise initiate".(Mosley, M.A., Lancaster, M., Parker, M.L. and Campbell, K., 2020,pp.1) This would implicate that the very foundational features of the online dating world are full of deception and tricks as people try to optimise their self-image in an environment which allows for this to occur.

The research design implemented within this study was qualitative and carried out via reddit, with the examination of threads pertaining to the shared and personal experiences with catfishing encounters. What this study has to offer is a comprehensive autoethnographic account of 'the catfish', using a blended theoretical basis drawing upon the disciplines of both sociology and anthropology with the application of both anomie and the trickster to aid in the interpretation of experiences in the field. The following is a demonstration of how both concepts work together with one another to help derive greater understanding of catfishing. Ultimately the catfish is variation of anomic structure and is used to set out and achieve certain operatives through non-conformist means and disbanding shortly after this. Whilst achieving certain pre-meditated, set goals is the main function of the catfish the actor behind this ultimately embodies trickster logic with using the false guise of another, and thus the resolution reached is that the catfish is the embodiment of the trickster in modernity.

I found that the more I delved into the world of the catfish in pursuit of answers I ended up with far more questions. Initially my first encounter in the field was on a reddit form dedicated for the open discussion of catfishing victim's personal experiences, the form was highly insightful at times and provided insight into personal experiences and the type of effects it solicited. However, it was difficult to establish trust with informants and there was a great deal of apprehension when it came down to answering any questions I may have had, at times I was even suspected as being a catfish myself. In the onset of my study, I came to realise very quickly that the type of informant demographic I was dealing with were extremely mistrusting and I can only speculate as to why coming to conclusion that their past experiences with strangers online didn't exactly fair well. I discovered from my submersion into the field that there's no 'standard' or typical catfishing procedure and oftentimes people are taken off guard due to the depths the catfish will go to make their online profile seem legitimate. In this view, people are completely unsuspecting and develop an emotional attachment to the person they are speaking, confiding in, and disclosing the intimacies of their daily life. As this connection furthers it becomes increasingly clear that the person, whom they are speaking is not real. Whilst in the field I did come to question how an individual could develop such a deep emotional connection with someone who was not in their immediate environment and there seemed to be a re-occurrence of a particular theme of people falling in love with the idea of being with someone rather. It is a common misconception that people who fall victim to

catfishing are gullible, and, in my view, it isn't fair to shift blame onto the victims for their perceived naivety in placing trust in someone who they had an emotional connection with as at one point the connection felt was very real. In most instances the catfish aims to deliberately target victims and extort them for money without the victims being inherently aware. The catfish's true intentions aren't entirely obvious, and it might begin with the catfish asking for smaller amounts of money. A prime example would be something like, "Hey, I'm going out for coffee with friends can you send me \$10, and I'll pay you back". There is also an entirely more sinister route for extortion by the catfish and that is developing a romantic connection with someone and taking part in the exchange of intimate photos and then threatening to leak these photos to friends, family, and the wider web as a form of revenge porn. Essentially the victims' intimate photos are held ransom for a certain sum of money. The two scenarios are both extremely damaging to the victim's mental wellbeing when they come to the realisation that the person who they built an emotional connection with was fictitious. This furthers my argument that just like the trickster, the catfish is at the threshold of human suffering and therefore the use of trickster logic is applicable thought the modern archetype of the catfish. The catfish has no morality and is similar to that of the trickster in that the trickster will make one forget where the boundaries of morality exist in order to successfully transgress them by simply shifting the yard posts with the logic of the ends justify the means by which they are achieved. This is extremely alarming in the sense that already we have an environment with no borders and issues with regulation, if the trickster's logic and mentality is to transgress borders it becomes dangerous in environments with little regulation and here the trickster logic has taken hold in my studied environment. From my own experience in the field there is very clear distinction between catfishing motives which can be broken down into two dimensional spheres which oftentimes intersect with one another. Catfishing is most used with intentions of malice for the exploitation of vulnerable members in society. However, extortion is not always at the forefront of catfishing and sometimes this is a deeply troubled individual who seeks attention, validation, companionship, and love. When it comes to the discussion around the catfish those would have the automatic assumption of victims and perpetrators, and when I initially began my exploration into the world of the catfish, I had this exact same assumption and my own assumptive ness was turned on its head and I would soon discover that this was seemingly incorrect.

Whilst in the field I stumbled across a reddit form which completely laughs in the face of this victim/perpetrator notion which dominates the social consciousness regarding the catfish. The reddit form was seemingly designed for individuals who wanted to be consensually catfished, and oftentimes would create threads giving clear instructions about how they wished to be catfished, even down to a preference in appearance, such as ethnicity, height, age, hair colour and so forth, it was seemingly a roleplay of sorts. It remains unclear to me why someone would wish to be intentionally catfished because it goes against all traditional notions. However, I have a theory regarding this, and it begs the question, is there some sort of gratification which may be achieved by this? Not only by the catfish which takes pleasure in deception but the person being actively deceived, like a gratification loop of sort with both individuals acting out a fictitious relationship and ultimately filling the void and the lack of attention, validation, companionship and love experienced IRL. "The ethical catfish", a viable solution to a problem? Is this the fulfilment of desires between two individuals without the emotional consequences of an unsuspecting misfortunate who believes they are speaking to the love of their life? or is this a practical joke between friends? it is important to consider that because this environment is full of deception it is at times difficult to decipher what actors' true motivations really are. It is indicative from anthropological literature that in modernity there are more tricksters now than ever before and I surmise that the use of trickster logic is a result of social pressures, and an increasing sense of hyper-individualism and more responsibility for oneself. To understand the phenomenon of the catfish it is wise to view modernity through a wider scope and we should begin to question who are we in modernity? and What are our core values and life philosophies? Modernity has changed its actors into Machiavellian characters, 'the ends justify the means' and as indicated by Arpad, the trickster "wishes to eat, drink and bedding, searching for any experience which brings pleasure and enjoyment, though this always combined with misgiving and anxiety that all might not end well". (Horvath Agnes, Szakolczai Arpad, 2020, pp114).

The catfish profile is temporary and only exists to achieve set means due to the ease in which online profiles may be created and subsequently deleted, ‘the thrill of the chase, the excitement of the catch and the spoils of the hunt’. In this view the catfish uses guerrilla ‘hit’ and run tactics in instances of extortion. If the catfish was to use the same profile consistently It would be compromised almost immediately so therefore, they are not made to be sustained, and as indicated in the offset with my hypothesis anomic structures facilitated by cyberspace are self-maintaining through a continual cycle of breakdown and re-constitution. The predominant life philosophy in modernity is to “live your best life” and in this sense we are all motivated to act with our own self-interest in mind to seek out novel experiences which bring us pleasure and thus employing a trickster life philosophy. To dissect the trickster in contemporaneity we need to surmise some motivations for the increased use of trickster logic. I imagine that people who have resorted to use trickster logic have succumbed to the pressures of modernity and employ trickster logic with incorporation of non-conformist means as a coping mechanism for the stresses of modern life. With all this considered it is also important to note that the pressures and stress of modern life and the use of trickster logic and anomie is not a cause-and-effect relationship, but rather modernity has created the optimal environment for trickster logic to be used as a coping mechanism for the pressures experienced in modernity. What is also very much apparent is the wider scale cultural dissemination which is facilitated by modern communication technology which pushes these social narratives and life philosophies.

A key characterisation of what it is to live in modernity is the increased sense of more responsibility for oneself, we are part of, yet devoid of human social relations, the experience of modernity is the increasing sense of distance between people and the social relations we maintain with others becoming estranged. This characterisation of modernity is not a new concept and is characterised in classical sociology with Émile Durkheim in his work ‘Le Suicide’, in which he addresses the problems of the 19th century industrial revolution in France and the feelings of alienation experienced by people. The industrial revolution of the 19th century coincides with increased feelings of responsibility for oneself and the dissolution of traditional notions of industry which were passed down from generation to generation and increased pressures of having to make something out of yourself. Subsistence in modernity is fraught with its own set challenges and in my view increased pressures to make something out of oneself coupled with the social narrative to live your best, fulfilled life, has indirectly influenced the social pathology of increased use of trickster logic and anomic means in modernity. Since the 19th century the pressures of modern life have not reached a plateau but has rather become much more of an issue because not only does one have to make something of oneself, but they also must experience happiness whilst doing it. In the past a career choice was chosen out of necessity, in modernity we choose a career choice based on the type of perceived happiness which may be generated from it.

Conclusion

The following section will provide a conclusion and summary of the research findings, how they addressed the research aims and questions, and provide demonstration in the value and contribution thereof and lastly make suggestion for further research. The main aims of research were to investigate catfishing phenomenon, to provide reasoning as to why people falsely present themselves online, and what makes one more susceptible to such trickery? The research findings implicate that cyberspace increases the likelihood in transgression of norms, fostering an environment with more anomic inducing effects, and secondly trickster logic is endemic to the human experience of cyber-space one of which we are all a part of a parade in performance. ‘all the world is a theatre, and all the men and women are but the actors. And all our lives we play

many parts' (Shakespeare William, 1623, Act 2, Scene 7). From what the research has shown gratification may be derived from the trickery of others, and paradoxically the individuals being tricked. The research findings addressed the research aims in the sense of working to uncover the reasoning for false presentation of self-online and would implicate that people aren't necessarily more susceptible to being catfished if they are actively trying to be deceived, as the findings suggest that people enjoy being tricked. The particular gaps which this study addressed is the application of a theoretical model of analysis, examining the wider phenomenon rather than from individual instances of catfishing, and how the structure of cyberspace not only allows for instances of catfishing to occur but increases the likelihood of this occurring. The contribution this study has made to the field of research in relation to theory and practice is the mapping out of how the data was both gathered and analysed in an orderly and coherent fashion, contributing to an already existent body of research, this may prove useful to researchers taking on future projects within this field who may replicate similar techniques and methodological practices. The use of particular theoretical framework in analysis may be applicable to varying context, this leads onto the next point, which is a suggestion for future research within this field. The initial research began with the possibility of looking at anomie and the trickster with cross cultural examination in varying geo-graphical context, this scope of research would prove far too wide to be undertaken in a singular study and did not meet the research aims and objectives established in the onset. However it is very likely that the particular insights which may be gained from this huge undertaking would prove highly valuable to this field of research and hence my suggestion holds validity.

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